

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	 University of Michigan Dept. of Archaeology Gabil Project
GPR	2011	B		Min: 62.923 Max: 63.3908	1320 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1467-69 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
yellowish layer within disturbance (SU)

Covered by SU: 0 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX														
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery f <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles f <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortar m <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) m <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails r <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Slag f <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) Bronzetakes in n/w corner of SU next to 1162	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) f <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) r <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	clay 5% silt 80% sand 15% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
Compaction	Color																
<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown																
<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown																
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White																
<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red																
<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow																
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)																

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit (old excavation limit 2010) Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: Is bound to (only for masonry):

Is abutted by: partially at NW by 1162 Abuts:

Is covered by: 0 Covers: 1384 1162 floor TBA # 1173

Is cut by: Cuts:

Is filled by: Fills: 1229

OBSERVATIONS
 Δ278 wotive vessel Δ283 iron plate

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: South Western corner ish, post 2010 excavation limit
 Shape: half oval

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): gradual slope ^{down} to the south (upper surface)
 gradual upward slope to the south (lower limit)
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): clusters of metal towards center
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): decreases as we approach southern limit
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

▲ = area w/ large pieces of slag

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:
 Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:
 Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

yellowish accumulation over tufa floor and over tile deposit along western limit, high frequencies of pottery and other debris suggest gradual accumulation. Originally we expected cut SU 1220 to extend to the edge of SU 1320, but it ended shortly to the south of our northern most SU limit.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by <i>Fabina Sam</i>	on <i>23/6/2011</i>
Revised by <i>CHH</i>	on <i>30/6/2011</i>
PDFd by	on
Entered by	on